

Chemistry in India : A short historical perspective and foundation of the Indian Chemical Society

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Preamble

It is now an established fact that in ancient India there was considerable development in the knowledge of Chemistry and ancient Indians acquired great skill in the application of such knowledge for the arts and comforts of life. This follows from many citations we come across in several of the sacred scriptures like the Vedas, the Upanishads, Puranas, etc. The traditional knowledge in the science of Chemistry, known to Indians as "Rasayan" since the time of Rigveda and Atharvaveda was developed further through the following several centuries that culminated in the compilations Charaka Sanghita and Susruta Sanghita. Indeed we Indians can rightly be proud of our very rich heritage.

A critical and fairly exhaustive and authentic account of the achievements of our ancestors is well documented by Prafulla Chandra Ray in a two-volume treatise "A History of Hindu Chemistry", vol. 1 (1902), vol. 2 (1909) published by the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works, Calcutta. This BCPW was the first venture in the field of chemical industry of modern India which was started in 1892 by Prafulla Chandra almost as a modest cottage industry using his personal meager savings and later (1901) this became a limited company and is presently a Government owned concern. A revised version (528 pages) of the first volume was published (1903) by William and Norgate, London. The topics covered in the first volume included in its six chapters, Chemistry in Charaka and Susruta, Chemistry in Vagbhata, Chemistry in Transitional (800-1100 AD) and Tantric (1100-1300 AD) Periods, Chemistry in Rasarnava (1300-1500 AD, known as Iatrochemical age), and Chemistry in Rasaratnasamuchaya. There are also sections dealing with metals and metallurgy, gunpowder, saltpetre, etc. In the concluding discussion there is a critical assessment of the causes of decline of scientific spirit in later periods.

In the second volume (published in 1909, revised in 1925) the major discussions are on Buddhist Alchemical Treatises and the Age of Nagarjuna (a renowned Alchemist, ca. 8th Century AD) and the later Iatrochemical period (1350-1600 AD). In this there is also a separate chapter on Mathematical and Physical and Chemical Theories of the Hindus by Brajendra Nath Seal.

The two volumes of History of Hindu Chemistry were the outcome of 15 years of painstaking work of Prafulla Chandra and this discovery and documentation of India's ancient heritage in Science was an important contribution of Prafulla Chandra. A fully revised and enlarged version of this treatise edited by Priyadarajan Ray, a very trusted pupil of Prafulla Chandra, was published subsequently (1956) by the Indian Chemical Society and is aptly titled "History of Chemistry in Ancient and Mediaeval India", in which new materials based on later findings have also been incorporated. Prafulla Chandra's comments in the preface to the second volume of *History of Hindu Chemistry* is worth noting :

"The Hindu nation with its glorious past and vast latent potentialities may yet look forward to a still glorious future, and, if the perusal of these pages will have the effect of stimulating my countrymen to strive to regain their old position in the intellectual hierarchy of nations, I shall not have laboured in vain."

The following remarks in a communication which P. C. Ray received from the renowned French Chemist M. P. E. Berthelot is worth noting :

"I have seen specially with pleasure how science with its universal and impersonal character is equally cultivated by all the civilized peoples of Asia as well as Europe and America."

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Modern School of Chemistry and the Indian Chemical Society

It is significant to note that during the period of 100 years from 1784-1883 only 24 papers in chemistry were published in the *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal*. Chemistry teaching was introduced in the Medical College, Calcutta, founded in 1835.

Even during the period since the forties of the nineteenth century only some chemistry related research works were carried out at a few centers in India. Thus, pioneering systematic work was carried out by Dr. W. B. O. Sharegnessy, Professor of Chemistry, Medical College, Calcutta, on the chemical and physiological properties of a large number of Indian herbs and drugs and the results were published in the Bengal Pharmacopoeia in 1840. Dr. D. Waldie investigated (1854) the monthly changes in the salinity of the Hooghly River Water, in Calcutta. Dr. K. L. Dey carried out work in 1860 on the medicinal plants of Bengal. Sir Alexander Pedler, Professor of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta, in collaboration with Chandra Bhusan Bhaduri, reported investigations of a more systematic nature on the coal gas and water supplies of Calcutta, Sir Pedler also worked on Cobra venom in collaboration with Sri P. B. Soor which was published in the *Proceedings of the Royal Society, London*. After many trials he also found PtCl_4 to be an antidote for the poison (tested on chicken). In 1890 he contributed three papers to the *Journal of the Chemical Society (London)* on the action of sunlight on some chemical reactions and the photoluminescence of phosphorus. Systematic teaching of modern chemistry in India was started by Sir Alexander Pedler in the Chemistry Department of Presidency College, Calcutta, in 1873; the credit for introduction of practical examinations in science subjects in the BA and MA courses of Calcutta University goes to him and he is also to be credited with first attempts to introduce physico-chemical research in India. He had his training in England under Sir Edward Frankland. He was an excellent teacher whose lectures were made interesting with experimental demonstrations.

Another name to be mentioned in connection with teaching of modern chemistry in India is that of Professor J. Campbell Oman, who was appointed Professor of Science in 1877 in the Government College, Lahore (now in Pakistan). Although he did not publish any original research paper from Lahore, he earned much reputation as a teacher whose class lectures were profusely illustrated with interesting experimental demonstrations. Mr. Oman retired in 1897, but it was only in 1906 that separate Chairs of Professors of Chemistry and of Physics were created in the

College at Lahore and Mr. B. Mouat Jones was the first to be appointed as Professor of Chemistry.

Research in Chemistry in modern India was really initiated much more systematically and actively by Prafulla Chandra Ray when he joined Presidency College, Calcutta, in June 1889 after he returned to India (in July 1888) armed with a D.Sc. degree of Edinburgh University (Scotland, UK). The first Indian who acquired the same honour (in 1875) was Aghore Nath Chattopadhyay, father of one of India's revered leaders of independence movement Sm. Sarojini Naidu (*née* Chattopadhyay) and Harindranath Chattopadhyay, and uncle of the present writer's maternal grandfather. Although some towering personalities like Prof. J. Van't Hoff expressed highly of Aghore Nath's intelligence and intellect, it is a misfortune of his countrymen that although he joined the Education Service in the Princely State of Hyderabad he never directed his efforts in the pursuit of and for the advancement of chemistry in India, a task which was aptly fulfilled by Prafulla Chandra and that too in an unfavourable situation in the country under alien rule. His first research work in India on chemical examination of fats and oils was published in the *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal*, 1894.

Any impartial and dispassionate assessment of Prafulla Chandra's personal contributions in research, as evident from many of his publications beginning with the so called mercurous nitrite (1896), hyponitrites (1897-1907), varying valency of platinum (1923) and gold (1924), shows that these are controversial and are in no way outstanding even in the context of contemporary knowledge in chemistry (*cf.* D. Banerjea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, **67**, 269 (1990)). The reported discovery of mercurous nitrite published in the *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal* (1896) was commented very favourably in the famous British weekly journal *Nature* (1896). P. C. Ray published a full paper on this in the *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, **71**, 348 (1897). But subsequent critical investigations by R. A. Potts and A. L. Allred (*Inorg. Chem.*, **5**, 1066 (1966)) have shown this to be non-existent. Attempts by the present writer to prepare the reported compound following the method of P. C. Ray and even modifications there of also ended in failure; the product (a yellow crystalline material) obtained being a basic nitrate of Hg(II) . But really speaking Prafulla Chandra's unique contributions, for which all Indians shall ever remain indebted to him, are his successful efforts in establishing an Indian School of Chemistry by inspiring and enthusing a band of devoted and dedicated young men who through their research contributions made a mark in the field of chemistry and several of them indeed earned interna-

tional recognition. In the words of one of his trusted and distinguished pupils, Jnanendra Nath Mukherjee,

"Outweighing his achievements as a scientific worker, the creation and fostering of an Indian School of Chemistry will ever remain his conspicuous contribution towards national progress of Indians."

Sir P. C. Ray's contributions in establishing the modern school of chemistry in India was acknowledged by Professor S. S. Bhatnagar, in his Presidential address in the Chemistry section of the Indian Science Congress session, 1928 :

"If a census were to be taken of all the Indian Chemists who have published any original work and if they were asked to indicate the source of their inspiration. I believe the majority would ascribe the credit to Sir P. C. Ray. The one atrocious crime which I have committed and for which, I am sure, I have not been forgiven by Sir P. C. Ray, is that I am not his pupil. My defence is that I was not born early enough and hence I happen to be a grand-pupil of his, having received instruction in Chemistry from the late Mr. Atul Chandra Ghosh, one of his earliest pupils."

In the same address Professor Bhatnagar acknowledged the activities of the School of Research at Calcutta as follows :

"To the mind of an Indian, Bengal still represents the intellectual province of India and Calcutta the metropolis."

"Calcutta is the undisputed birthplace of modern chemical research in this country."

A landmark development in the pursuit of Science in modern India was the establishment (1876) in Calcutta of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science by Dr. Mahendra Lal Sircar, a renowned medical practitioner of his time, as a personal initiative, for the cultivation and promotion of Science by Indians, following the model of the British Association for the Advancement of Science. This premier institute of India is now one of the several national institutes fully funded by the Department of Science and Technology of Government of India's Ministry of Science and Technology. This institute became particularly famous when in 1928 C. V. Raman working in this institute published his discovery of what later became known as the Raman Effect which earned him the Nobel Prize in Physics of 1930. Formation of the Indian Science Congress Association in 1914, in Calcutta, which was primarily the result of joint efforts of Professor McMohan, Professor of Chemistry, Canning College, Lucknow, and Professor J. L. Simonsen, Professor of Chemistry, Presidency College,

Madras, was another landmark development. This association provided a platform for interaction of Indian scientists of different disciplines at the annual Science Congress sessions of this association. Research works were presented in different sections of the annual congress session, Chemistry being one of those. The abstracts of the papers as were submitted for presentation were printed in the Proceedings, and this practice is still in vogue. Even after the foundation of the Indian Chemical Society in 1924 this Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress continued to provide a forum for an annual session of the Indian Chemical Society (and similarly for several other sister societies) upto 1960 or so. The journal *Everyman's Science* is published by the Indian Science Congress Association.

In 1900 Jamsetjee N. Tata made a princely gift valued Sterling Pound 200,000 to the Government for the establishment of an institute for post-graduate studies and research in science for Indians. The Government invited Sir William Ramsay to submit a scheme for this purpose. A vivid description of Sir William Ramsay's impressions of scientific education then prevailing in India and his recommendations is to be found in the Presidential address of Professor S. S. Bhatnagar delivered in the Chemistry Section of the Science Congress session, 1928. Space does not permit to mention the same. Ramsey's recommendations were examined by a Committee consisting of Professor Sir Orme Masson and Colonel Clibborn (then Principal, Roorkee College). Based on the final recommendation, The Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, was established with Dr. M. W. Travers, FRS, as the first Director, in 1906, and the first batch of students were admitted into the institute in 1911. This IISc, Bangalore, is presently one of the foremost centers of higher studies and research in several frontier areas of modern science in the disciplines of Chemistry and Physics. Incidentally, the Central College, Bangalore (now under Bangalore University) also maintained high standard of research in various fields, a few significant such contributions of the early days (in the second decade of the 20th century) being on the possible mechanism of photosynthesis in green plants (carried out in collaboration with J. H. Priestley), action of radium emanation on the elements of the carbon group (carried out in collaboration with Sir William Ramsey), determination of ozone and oxides of nitrogen in the atmosphere by B. Sanjiva Rao which was carried out under Professor F. L. Usher (of this college).

Another landmark was foundation of the Bose Institute by Sir Jagadis Chandra Bose in 1917 at Calcutta, with the objects "for advancement of knowledge by means of research and diffusion of knowledge by organizing discourses,

demonstrations and lectures." After independence, the financial responsibility of this institute has been fully taken over by the Department of Science and Technology of the Government of India. Traditionally, the contributions of this institute in the fields of physical and life sciences have been commendable; some aspects of chemical sciences are also pursued in this institute, although these are truly not in any of the so-called hard core areas of chemical science. Jagadis Chandra Bose (born, 1858) was a contemporary of Prafulla Chandra Ray (born, 1861) but by all considerations was the most brilliant scientific luminary of 19th century India, who pioneered scientific research of high quality. But unlike Sir P. C. Ray, Sir J. C. Bose did not establish a school to carry forward his legacy.

Nil Ratan Dhar, a pupil of Sir P. C. Ray, had his first paper published in the *J. Chem. Soc. (London)* with P. C. Ray, in 1912. Subsequently, research papers on a variety of topics of conventional Physical Chemistry started emerging steadily from Professor N. R. Dhar's laboratory at Allahabad. Indeed, N. R. Dhar, J. C. Ghosh, J. N. Mukherjee and S. S. Bhatnagar rightly deserve the credit for establishing the modern active school of research in Physical Chemistry in India. Some of the most significant contributions of J. C. Ghosh, J. N. Mukherjee and S. S. Bhatnagar were in the fields of electro-chemistry and photo-chemistry, colloid chemistry, and magneto-chemistry, respectively. J. C. Ghosh spent several years of his career at Dacca University (now in Bangladesh). This university also became an excellent center of research in Organic Chemistry with Dr. E. R. Watson's contributions on colour and constitution and of Dr. B. K. Singh's on optical activity. Meanwhile Professor B. B. Dey, also a pupil of Sir P. C. Ray, established an active school of research in Organic Chemistry at Presidency College of Madras University. This Madras University was founded in 1857 with the universities of Calcutta and of Bombay, being the first three Universities to be set up in modern India in 1857, Calcutta University being the oldest.

Setting up of the University College of Science and Technology of Calcutta University in 1914 provided a booster to the advancement of scientific and technological education in India, and the credit for this is primarily due to Sir Asutosh Mookerjee.

Priyadarajan Ray, a very trusted pupil of Sir P. C. Ray, similarly deserves the credit of establishing the modern school of research in Inorganic Chemistry and Analytical Chemistry in India at Calcutta. He was also a pioneer in the fields of microchemistry and magnetochemistry. Sir P. C. Ray spoke of P. Ray as follows :

"Priyadarajan Ray is regarded as an acknowledged authority on complexes and valency and also on microchemistry and it is my practice to submit my own papers to his criticism and judgement before they are contributed to the chemical societies. My presidential addresses at the annual meetings of the Indian Chemical Society of 1926 and 1929 are based mainly upon his ideas and suggestions. A more silent and unobtrusive worker is seldom to be met with."

Significantly, Sir P. C. Ray allowed P. Ray and also J. N. Mukherjee to publish their research papers independently from the beginning. The first publication of P. Ray (who later became Sir Taraknath Palit Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University) appeared in a well-known German journal (*Z. Anorg. Chem.*) in 1912. Later on Professor P. Ray became an acknowledged authority in the fields of Coordination Chemistry, Magnetochemistry and Microanalytical Chemistry. He played an important and active role in the establishment of the Inorganic Chemistry Department of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, in 1951, and served as its first Professor, after his retirement from the Calcutta University in 1952. The present writer was the first Research Fellow of this department. As a student of Prof. P. Ray the present writer happens to be a grand-pupil of Sir P. C. Ray.

In those early days of the last century Indian workers used to get their research work published in the *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal*, which was hardly a science journal in a true sense, or else in some of the foreign journals of England and European countries like Germany and France, and the USA. By 1919 many Indian chemists felt that research publications of Indian Chemists were so scattered in many foreign journals of different geographic regions of the world that it was difficult under the then prevailing conditions to have a comprehensive view of Indian contributions. Some Indian chemists also felt that the foreign journals, owing to much demand, were not considering favourably many of the Indian contributions for publication, even in cases where the quality was at par with many of the foreign contributions. Moreover, there used to be considerable delay in getting papers published in foreign journals which was a serious hurdle in competitive science. While many considered that a paper published in a foreign journal would receive better recognition (unfortunately this attitude still continues with many) there was more or less a unanimous feeling that an Indian journal would be the appropriate medium for publication of Indian work, as is true of the national journals of many other countries.

A positive step to achieve this objective was a discus-

sion of the matter by Jnanendra Nath Mukherjee, Jnan Chandra Ghosh and Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar held in October, 1919 in the Physical Chemistry Laboratory of Professor F. G. Donnan in the University College, London (of University of London) where the above named were carrying out their higher studies and research in Chemistry for D.Sc. degree of London University. This discussion as mentioned by Professor Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar in his Presidential Address in Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress session of 1928, is quoted below :

"I crave your indulgence for a few minutes to disclose the account of a private conference which Dr. Ghosh, Dr. Mukherjee and I had in the year 1919 in the University College Chemical Laboratories in London. The subject-matter of our conference was the starting of an All India Chemical Society, with Sir P. C. Ray as its first President. We had a long discussion on the subject and afterwards we took Professor Donnan into our confidence and he fully approved of the plan. On our return to India out of the many plans which we made together and of all of which Dr. J. N. Mukherjee was to be the custodian, the one which he did not forget to carry out was the founding of the Indian Chemical Society. The President and the Secretary constitute the life and soul of a learned Society and if one of them happens to be a colloidal chemist, the success of the Society is by tradition ensured. Take, for example, the case of the Chemical Society, London, which we all recognize as the parent of our Indian Chemical Society. The first President of that Society was Thomas Graham, the father of Colloidal Chemistry. By a curious chance Dr. Mukherjee, who is the first Secretary of the Indian Chemical Society happens to be the father of Colloidal Chemistry in our country, and may we hope from this that our Society will have as glorious and distinguished a record as the parent Society in London, early discussion for whose establishment were also held in the University College Chemical Laboratories in London."

Pursuant to this discussion and the communication which they individually had with fellow chemists in India and some leading personalities in the field of chemistry in foreign countries they were convinced that their plan for establishment of an Indian Chemical Society and a journal to be published by the Society would receive the whole-hearted support of many, although a few expressed dissenting note.

On their return to India the trio, particularly Jnanendra Nath Mukherjee, earnestly took up implementation of their plan for establishment of an Indian Chemical Society, and

a proposal was formally moved at the Indian Science Congress session (1922) at Madras by Professor Nil Ratan Dhar (another pupil of Prafulla Chandra) who was President of the Chemistry Section of the said Science Congress session. Pursuant to this a committee was formed with the following members to take steps for implementation of the decision :

Dr. Caldwell, Dr. B. B. Dey, Dr. R. L. Datta, Dr. G. J. Fowler, Mr. Moudgill, Dr. J. N. Mukherjee, Dr. K. G. Naik, Dr. B. K. Singh, Dr. J. L. Simonsen and Dr. E. R. Watson (Convener)

This committee was later designated as the Executive Committee with Dr. E. R. Watson as President and Dr. J. N. Mukherjee as Secretary. A Sub-committee of the following members was also formed at Madras and the members were asked to meet the same evening for finalisation of the plan of action to follow :

Dr. E. R. Watson (President), Dr. J. L. Simonsen, Dr. R. L. Datta and Dr. J. N. Mukherjee (Convener and Secretary)

The Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress nominated Dr. Nil Ratan Dhar to both the above Committees. This Sub-committee at its meeting resolved that the Indian Chemical Society be established and that the Society shall undertake the publication of a journal for chemical science.

Since the question of funding was important (estimated cost Rs. 20000 p.a. for publication of the journal) a proposal was made by Professor J. L. Simonsen to bring out the journal as part of the *Proceedings of the Asiatic Society of Bengal* (this is now the Asiatic Society, an Institute of National Importance recognized and funded by the Government of India). But no further steps were taken in the matter as it was felt that the said Royal Asiatic Society of Bengal will not be able to help in the matter. Incidentally, the said Royal Asiatic Society of Bengal was founded by Sir William Jones in the year 1784.

After returning to Calcutta from Madras Dr. J. N. Mukherjee took up the responsibility of founding the Indian Chemical Society most sincerely and in right earnest. Initially Dr. Watson personally met all expenses on correspondence, etc., which was later made good out of fellowship subscription. Dr. J. N. Mukherjee then approached the most revered Sir Asutosh Mookerjee, then Vice-Chancellor of Calcutta University, who was well known for his keen interest in the promotion of higher education in the country and advancement of the boundaries of knowledge, for necessary aid and assistance for the publication of the journal. Sir Asutosh blessed Dr. Mukherjee and assured him that

the journal shall be printed at the Calcutta University Press at a cost not exceeding Rs. 1500 (a very decent sum in those days) and the formal sanction in the matter was conveyed by the Registrar, Calcutta University, in a letter dated 7.5.1922. Dr. Jnan Chandra Ghosh, then at Dacca (now in Bangladesh) conveyed Dacca University's sanction of Rs. 200 as annual grant for the purpose and the University of Allahabad and Punjab University, Lahore (now in Pakistan) also sanctioned annual grant of Rs. 200 and Rs. 100 respectively. Later on several other universities of India also sanctioned token annual grants. The arrangement for printing the journal in the Calcutta University Press continued for many years, but later on for various reasons the University of Calcutta withdrew this facility but sanctioned an annual grant of Rs. 5000 in lieu of the said facility and this continued even as late as the mid seventies of the last century when the present writer was the Honorary Secretary of the Society. It is indeed regrettable that in the course of the next decade or two all the universities stopped payment of their grants to the Society. Even a token annual grant of Rs. 2000 from each one of the nearly 250 universities in India can be of great help to the Indian Chemical Society to partly tide over its present financial crisis.

At meetings of the above Sub-committee and Committee held at Lucknow in January 1923 it was finally decided that the Indian Chemical Society be established and publication of a quarterly journal be started. The Indian Chemical Society was then formally founded as a Registered Society on 9th May, 1924 with 101 Fellows and a Council of the following composition :

The Members of the Council and Office-Bearers in 1924

President	Sir P. C. Ray, K.T., C.I.E., Ph.D., D.Sc.
Vice-Presidents	Gilbert J. Fowler, D.Sc., F.I.C. J. L. Simonsen, D.Sc., F.I.C., F.A.S.B. E. R. Watson, M.A., D.Sc.
Secretary	J. N. Mukherjee, D.Sc.
Treasurer	P. C. Mitter, M.A., Ph.D.
Editors	N. R. Dhar, D.Sc., F.I.C., Dr.es.Sc. A. N. Meldrum, D.Sc.

Members of the Council

H. E. Annett, D.Sc.	K. G. Naik, D.Sc.
S. S. Bhatnagar, D.Sc.	A. R. Normand, Ph.D.
R. L. Datta, D.Sc., F.R.S.E.	H. K. Sen, M.A., D.Sc., D.I.C.
B. B. Dey, D.Sc., F.I.C.	R. N. Sen, M.A., M.Sc.
J. C. Ghosh, D.Sc.	B. K. Singh, D.Sc.
D. D. Karve, Ph.D.	B. H. Wilsdon

Choice of the first President of the Society, which was very aptly mentioned by Professor J. N. Mukherjee, is quoted below :

"The choice of President of the Society was a difficult affair as claims from many persons were being received. But there was no difficulty in declaring Professor Prafulla Chandra Ray as the first President and he was also designated as founder President in recognition of and a tribute to his pioneering services in chemical research in India. He had however no active part in the foundation of the Society."

Incidentally, the Indian Science News Association was founded in 1935 with Sir P. C. Ray as its first President. The Journal *Science and Culture* is published by this Association.

To begin with, the Indian Chemical Society had no office of its own and it functioned from the Secretary Professor J. N. Mukherjee's room in the University College of Science, Calcutta. Sir. P. C. Ray came forward and made a gift of Rs. 10000 to the Calcutta University for building a house for the Society. This happily resulted in 1933 in the construction of three large rooms, in the third storey of the south wing of Sir Taraknath Palit Building at the University College of Science and Technology, Calcutta, two of which were placed permanently for the use of the Society and the third one for use of the University; the Society is still housed in this location.

In 1967, the Society acquired from the Calcutta Improvement Trust a 10 cottah plot of land at Maniktala, Calcutta, on lease for a long term of 99 years at a cost of about Rupees one lakh and ten thousand for construction of its own building. The foundation stone for the building was laid by Professor J. N. Mukherjee on August 2, 1970; August 2, 1861 being the date of birth of P. C. Ray. But construction of this Sir P. C. Ray memorial building could not be started so far due to lack of funds, and unless the Government comes to provide the needed financial assistance there is not likely to be a solution in the near future. All appeals made so far have yielded no result.

The first issue of the quarterly journal of the Indian Chemical Society was published in November 1924.

The Society and its Journal were welcomed by different sister Societies abroad. Professor Wynne, President of the Chemical Society, London, cabled to Dr. P. C. Ray, "Heartly congratulations and warm wishes to the newly formed Indian Chemical Society." Dr. P. C. Ray in his reply to Professor Wynne expressed the reasons for founding a Chemical Society in India, as follows :

"The journal of the Chemical Society (of London) has hitherto been the only organ of chemists throughout the British Empire, and the Publication Committee had been hard put to it to find space for the ever-increasing number of communications and have often been under the necessity of appealing to authors of papers to abridge them as far as possible. This branch of science (chemistry) was zealously pursued in ancient India, and I have now the satisfaction of finding chairs of Chemistry in most universities of India filled by my own pupils, who have also been regular contributors to the Journal of the Chemical Society (London)."

The quality of publications in the journal at the initial stages was recognized to be fairly high as would be apparent from the following report published in *Nature (London)* :

"The great work in chemistry which has occurred in the Indian Empire during the past ten years, had led to the establishment of an Indian Chemical Society; the first number of the Quarterly journal of the Society has now appeared."

"Apart, from the pleasure with which all British chemists will welcome this national effort on the part of India, there will be general agreement among them that the scheme of decentralization of publications within the British Empire which it implies is the only one which lead to the rapid and adequate publication of new knowledge and tend ultimately to the real advancement of chemistry."

"The new Journal is a welcome illustration of the development which has taken place in Indian Chemistry during recent years. There are thirteen papers, and only one of these is published under the English names. The remaining papers are published by Indians and come from all parts of the Indian Empire. Four of these emanate from the College of Science, Calcutta, and this is as it should be, because, for many years past, this institution has been the back-bone of chemical research in India."

The journal became bimonthly in 1928 and is now monthly since 1930. In 1937, in collaboration with the Institution of Chemists (India) the *Industrial and News Edition* of the journal was introduced to meet the requirements of industrial chemists and this was published as a separate quarterly periodical. In 1958 this was replaced by *Indian Journal of Applied Chemistry*. But due to a dearth of adequate number of papers appropriate for such a journal in the course of time and particularly since the early seventies of the last century, its publication as a separate journal has

been discontinued since 1973 and the few communications in the field of industrial and applied chemistry as are received are published in the *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society* in which there are the following major sections : Inorganic Chemistry, Physical Chemistry, Organic Chemistry, Analytical Chemistry, Biochemistry, and Industrial and Applied Chemistry.

In recent years the Society has adopted a policy to publish some of the monthly issues as special issues having mostly invited papers, articles and reviews, in honour of some of its distinguished Fellows, as is decided by the Council.

Since inception the Society established exchange agreement for sending its journal to sister Societies in exchange of receiving journals published by those societies. This agreement was with 10 journals in 1924 and the figure rose to 128 in 1948 and was 125 in the year 2003. The number of papers published in the first issue was 23 and this rose to 107 in 1948, 404 in 1972 and 237 in the year 2003. The number of Fellows increased from 101 in 1924 to 393 in 1929, 448 in 1948, 1200 in 1973, 2534 in 2001, but 2192 in 2002 and 2447 in 2003. The number of non-fellow subscribers (universities, institutes) of the journal was 289 in 1948, 750 (350 Indian, 400 foreign) in 1973, but 323 (250 Indian, 73 foreign) in 2002 and 321 (254 Indian and 67 foreign) in 2003. In this connection the following observations of Professor P. Ray in his address at the opening ceremony of the Golden Jubilee Session (1973) is worth noting (as this is still relevant) :

"These figures, though not very encouraging in spite of strenuous efforts and planning for the rapid development of science and scientific industry in the country by the National Government, still represents the dynamic state of the Society. But so far as the quality of its publications is concerned, the Society, it must be admitted, has considerable leeway to make up."

Since 1963 the Indian Chemical Society is holding an Annual Convention of Chemists in which invited lectures and Endowment Lectures of the Society are organized in all the conventional major branches of chemistry and oral and poster presentations of papers by relatively younger chemists are also arranged. There is provision for some Convention Awards for the papers so presented and assessed both for quality of the contribution and its presentation. The number of Endowment awards is 17 at present including the few most prestigious ones in memory of P. C. Ray, P. Ray, J. C. Ghosh and J. N. Mukherjee, while there are 13 Convention awards, several being in memory of some of our distinguished Fellows, as per the wishes of the donors.

In a vast country like India with many active centers of research spread all over the length and breadth of the country, east to west and north to south, proper decentralization of activities of the Society is a necessity. Hence, provisions were made in the Rules and Regulations of the Society for establishment of Branches of the Society in different regions/cities of our country. Indeed the Society has several such Branches which organize regional scientific programmes. But there is no denying that their activities need to be enhanced and widened and that more such active centres ought to come up in the future.

The Society has provision for bestowing Honorary Fellowship to those of any nationality who have attained eminence by their immense contributions to chemistry and chemical industry. This selection was done very judiciously in earlier years. Several of our Honorary Fellows in the past

and a few at present were/are Nobel Laureates and other eminent personalities.

It is a pity that despite being the oldest scientific society in the field of chemistry in India and the most important role it has played since inception for the cultivation, promotion and advancement of chemistry at the national level with international recognition, it has not as yet received the patronage of our National and State Governments and other agencies to the extent it rightly deserves, such that it can further its activities to serve the nation.

I wish to conclude by quoting the following words from a speech delivered by Sir P. C. Ray in a meeting of the Senate of the Calcutta University in December 1922 :

"We should see that the noble heritage which has been granted to us is not bartered for a mess of pottage."

Note added in proof

On the instability of mercurous nitrite :

Based on following literature data (*cf.* "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 61st ed., (Ed.) R. C. West, The CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida, USA, 1980; "Inorganic Chemistry", 4th ed., J. C. Huheey *et al.*, Harper Collins, New York, USA, 1993; "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 6th ed., F. A. Cotton *et al.*, John Wiley, New York, USA, 1999),

which is based on,

the ΔH value for,

is 1068 kJ mol⁻¹.

This high endothermicity accounts for the non-existence (high instability) of Hg₂(NO₂)₂ in gaseous state.

Again, from the following literature data (*loc. cit.*),

the lattice energy, U_o , for the conversion of 2HgCl(g) to solid Hg₂Cl₂(c) is,

$$U_o = -423.9 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$$

Since the ionic radius of Cl⁻ (1.81 Å) is close to that for NO₂⁻ (1.78 Å) and since according to Kapustinskii equation U_o in kcal mol⁻¹ is,

$$U_o = -289.2 \left(\frac{\nu Z_+ Z_-}{r_+ + r_-} \right) \left(1 - \frac{0.345}{r_+ + r_-} \right), r \text{ in } \text{Å unit},$$

$$\text{and for Hg}_2\text{X}_2 \quad \nu = 3, Z_+ = 2, Z_- = 1,$$

the corresponding U_o value for formation of Hg₂(NO₂)₂(c) from 2HgNO₂(g) is expected to be *ca.* -424 kJ mol⁻¹ as for Hg₂Cl₂.

$$\text{For Hg}(l) \longrightarrow \text{Hg}(g), \Delta H = 61.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$$

Therefore, for the process,

2Hg(l) + 2NO₂(g) → Hg₂(NO₂)₂(c), the ΔH value is expected to be *ca.* 1273 kJ mol⁻¹. Hence, crystalline Hg₂(NO₂)₂(c) is also expected to be too unstable.